

Marginal Gains

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

The Marginal Gains workshop method instigates the participants to look for **quick wins**, the little things that could easily be done, adding up to great improvements. It is a group activity for identifying, framing and refining intentions, target outcomes and success criteria.

Benefits

This fosters collaborative brainstorming resulting in small, actionable improvements, leading to a more comprehensive and refined proposal.

Practical recommendations

1. Share the 100 things by 1% improvement idea, and explain the intention for this activity:
 "It's very difficult to improve 1 thing by 100%. It's much easier to improve 100 things by 1% for the same effect." This is the 100 things by 1% improvement idea by Dave Brailsford.
 "We want to talk about all the little things which might help us improving".
2. Define what you mean by quick wins
 "A quick win is something that could be implementable in a couple of hours, with very little cost." You are free to adapt this definition to what you are seeking exactly.
3. Ask everyone to individually brainstorm on quick wins for project proposal improvements, writing each idea on a post-it.
4. Collect all post-its and place on a board while grouping them.
5. Discuss the quick wins (filtering activity).

Credit: This workshop format is sourced from FunRetrospectives (<https://www.funretrospectives.com/>). This activity was shared by Steve Wells. It is inspired on the philosophy of Dave Brailsford, head of Team Sky. This activity is shared under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Transparent communication about agenda's, expectations, and results

Work with a diversity of professional backgrounds

Recognition of, and work with, the limitations of different organisations

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Link to Marginal Gains by FunRetrospectives](#)

*right click to open

Figure: Quick wins brainstorm